

1 **PTPN22 functions in fine control of execution of immunologic tolerance.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We describe here T-cell activation defects resulting from mutation of the PTPN22 gene at S325. Stag2
8 appeared to be a major effector of PTPN22 function. Nuclear factor mobilization downstream of PTPN22
9 included Sp4, Id3 and Pax6. PTPN22 S325A mutation resulted in silencing of RORC. Innate immunologic
10 consequences of PTPN22 intracellular tail mutation included NLRP3 and CARD6 activation, Ifi44 silencing
11 and IL4R activation. PTPN22 controlled expression of the MHC class II molecules HLA-DRB1 and
12 HLA-DRB5. Granzyme A (GZMA) was a major downstream cellular effector of PTPN22 immunologic
13 function.

14 Citations

15 1. Siminovitch, K.A., 2004. PTPN22 and autoimmune disease. *Nature genetics*, 36(12),
16 pp.1248-1249.

17 2. Stanford, S.M. and Bottini, N., 2014. PTPN22: the archetypal non-HLA autoimmunity gene. *Nature*
18 *Reviews Rheumatology*, 10(10), pp.602-611.